

Original Article

How Customer Loyalty and Satisfaction Influences Strategic Market Management

Zara Khan^{1*}, Irwa khan²

¹Qurtuba University of Science and Technology, Peshawar

²Sir Syed University of Engineering and Technology, Karachi - Pakistan

Abstract

Effective strategic management highly depends on understanding customer loyalty and satisfaction's pull and push in fiercely competitive business setup. Consequently, this research seeks to evaluate interactive roles played by these vital elements in influencing strategies put in place by marketers. Customer satisfaction, considered as a primary antecedent of loyalty, can be assessed along product quality, excellence in services and perceived value just to mention but a few examples. In this research, we will investigate how maintaining customer satisfaction results in customer loyalty, thereby decreasing the costs of acquisition, increasing profitability as well as customer retention through loyalty programs which are some of the ways of implementing strategic market management with customer loyalty such as CRM, customer-managed relationships and personalized customer programs. A detailed examination of current literature and secondary data will reveal best practices and new perspectives that organizations might use to embody client contentment and faithfulness within their strategic frameworks. These results serve as a reminder to all industries about the importance of making customer oriented decisions so that they remain ahead in competition while ensuring steady growth of their territory.

Keywords: Customer loyalty, Customer retention, Customer satisfaction, Perceived value, Strategic market management

1. INTRODUCTION

Any company's interactions with its market must be focused on the needs of its customers (Kohli & Jaworski, 1990) Customer orientation, which is the core element of market orientation, is a significant factor in corporate performance (Nurfarida et al., 2021). Companies need to concentrate on increasing client satisfaction and loyalty in the competitive business environment of today if they want to stay ahead of the competition. Consumer loyalty and satisfaction are important variables that can have a big impact on strategic market management. These may have an impact on a business's market share, client loyalty, and reputation as a brand. Due to the market's high level of uncertainty, senior management struggles to win customers' loyalty (Aramburu & Pescador, 2019). Several

businesses have struggled to increase their levels of client loyalty and profit but failed because of the management's inadequate policies and strategies, and the final product's unsatisfactory quality (Wolter et al., 2017).

Due to a lack of management customer attraction, firms typically don't care enough about the demands and wishes, attitudes, and trends of their consumers (Herhausen et al, 2019). As a result, many businesses have lost their past clients and are unable to find new ones because good client connections can be built through the attraction of new consumers and their long-term retention (Khan et al., 2020). Customer loyalty does not happen easily, though. Businesses must invest a great deal of effort, money, and time (Izogo, 2017). Customers are less likely to switch to competition when they are happy and devoted. Because they don't

Article History

Received	March 05, 2024
Revised	April 20, 2024
Accepted	April 23, 2024
Published	May 31, 2024

Copyright © The Author(s). 2024

This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribute 4.0 International License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author(s) and source are credited.

How to cite:

Khan, Z., & khan, I. (2024). How Customer Loyalty and Satisfaction Influences Strategic Market Management: A Literature Survey. *Sustainable Business Management Review*, 1(2), 49-54.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13224427>

have to spend as much on attracting new clients, businesses can lower their marketing expenses.

According to studies, businesses that consistently achieve high levels of customer satisfaction see significant increases in profitability (Fornell et al, 2010). Companies must constantly evaluate market trends and competitive dynamics in order to find the most efficient tactics for attaining their objectives in terms of strategic market management. To keep ahead of the competition, this may entail creating new goods or services, entering new markets, or changing pricing or promotional tactics. Concepts like strategy, strategic thinking, and strategic management inspire reverence and awe. There isn't a single strategy that would work well for all businesses. Each business must determine the course that, given the available options, seems the most rational while taking into consideration its unique possibilities, goals, and resources (Zsigmond et al., 2021).

The techniques and ideas of strategic management should evolve to reflect the shifting nature of the global economy. Many aspects and concerns should be included in the strategic management of businesses (Joyce & Woods, 1996). Decisions, actions, and emotions that raise the chances of succeeding and lower the possibility of objective failure make up a strategy. So, every company plan is a special work of art (Magretta, 2012). Being able to attain balance and gain a competitive advantage is extremely difficult because both the company environment and client needs are always changing. The ideas can be diverse and unique if the strategy can develop them and see them from many angles.

Effective objectives and missions in a changing global corporate environment must be clear, adaptive, inspiring, and measurable; they must be simple to comprehend but not overly simple for customers and other stakeholders; they must be realistic in terms of chronology but contain quality (Mura & Sleziak, 2014). Despite customer loyalty and satisfaction are becoming increasingly significant in the current competitive industry, little is known about how they influence strategic market management. It is crucial to consider how customer loyalty and satisfaction might affect the creation and implementation of successful marketing strategies as businesses aim for continuous growth and profitability.

Rationale

Despite the significance of customer happiness and loyalty, there is still a lack of

knowledge regarding how these aspects affect strategic market management, particularly in light of the dynamic and ever-changing nature of today's marketplace. In order to achieve long-term success, doing a thorough analysis of these issues can offer insightful information about how firms can manage customer relationships successfully and create marketing plans that are in line with client wants and preferences.

Significance

Due to its ability to offer insightful knowledge into consumer behavior and preferences, the study of the effects of customer loyalty and satisfaction on strategic market management is important because it can eventually improve corporate performance and profitability. This study explains how consumer satisfaction and loyalty influence the strategic management of markets. Consequently firms can appreciate the importance of building consumer contentment for sustaining client loyalty—and in the long run, realizing growth that is sustainable. Through synthesizing theories already present in the mass of literature in this subject area, the study intends to contribute to customer loyalty theories and satisfaction theories. It can improve upon existing models as well as consider possible new ones that would more accurately reflect complexities found in current consumer behaviour patterns within markets

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

We quickly review the literature, focusing on its importance in comprehending the connection between customer loyalty, satisfaction, and strategic market management. Customer loyalty, which expresses consumers' dedication to and preference for a particular brand or product, is a crucial component of corporate success. Loyal clients frequently decide to work with a specific business, making recurring purchases and promoting the brand. Positive interactions, contentment with the good or service, and the development of an emotional bond are frequently the foundations around which this loyalty is established. Customers rely on brands that consistently fulfil their promises, thus trust and dependability are important.

Additionally, by displaying a thorough awareness of individual preferences, customization and customized experiences can further increase loyalty. Long-term client loyalty can also be fostered by implementing loyalty programmes and offering incentives and prizes. Creating a loyal client base is a strategic necessity

since it encourages keeping clients. When customers are said to be “loyal,” that loyalty may be shown to the brand (Yi & Jeon, 2003). Customer retention, according to Anderson and Narus (1998), is a more successful business approach than attempting to consistently bring in new clients to take the place of the departing ones. If a business wants to keep its current clients, it needs to have loyal customers. However, there are numerous arguments over what exactly constitutes customer loyalty.

According to Gupta and Sahu (2015), customer loyalty is a complex, multidimensional concept. A strongly held determination to repeatedly purchase or use a favoured good or service, despite external factors and marketing initiatives having the potential to cause switching behaviour (Oliver, 1997). According to Terblanche and Boshoff (2006), loyalty is a long-term attitude and a long-term behavioural pattern that is reinforced by numerous encounters over time. They provide empirical as well as personal proof to support this claim. It is proposed that customer delight is a concept linked to satisfaction but distinct from it. Dissatisfaction is similar to, but different from, satisfaction in this way.

Customer pleasure necessitates that customers receive a positive surprise that is beyond their expectations, whereas satisfaction is typically based on matching or exceeding one's expectations. This idea is supported empirically by Bowen and Chen (2001). The study examined the relationship between customer loyalty to Mercedes-Benz USA and customer satisfaction levels. The findings showed that the likelihood of an unhappy consumer returning back business was only 10%. If the consumer was happy with the goods and service, there was a 29% chance that they would purchase the same item or rent it again. However, it was discovered that 86% of happy consumers were likely to do business with the company again. Customer satisfaction or dissatisfaction is an affective or cognitive response to a single or extended sequence of service experiences.

However, there are two basic ways that satisfaction is interpreted in the literature: as a process and as an outcome (Gustafsson et al., 2015). Therefore, satisfaction can be defined as an assessment judgement of preference in relation to a certain purchasing decision. Customer satisfaction in this study refers to how satisfied consumers are with the products and services, as well as how successfully businesses have been able to draw in and keep customers. Customers desire high-value services to the extent that they

spend their time and money on them. In other terms, customer satisfaction is the popularity a consumer gains as a result of a product's various qualities. Additionally, it provides a source of income and motivates them to continue with their interests.

Customer satisfaction is defined in the business world as the general attitude a customer has towards the services and goods of a service provider. Over the past few years, customer loyalty—defined as a consumer's consistent favourable purchase behaviour towards a particular business or brand—has also been held accountable for customer pleasure. Customer satisfaction is the primary component in determining a customer's loyalty, and it also has the capacity to affect a customer's loyalty and future purchase intentions (Machirori & Fatoki, 2014). Kotler (2007) was one of the first to make the argument that performance that meets expectations is associated with satisfaction whereas performance that falls short of expectations is associated with disappointment. According to a widely accepted definition, satisfaction is the emotion that an individual has when comparing the perceived output of a product to his or her expectations (Körner et al., 2015).

This demonstrates that consumers will be disappointed if the perceived production is lower than expected. Otherwise, if the results match the anticipated expectations, consumers would be neutral or indifferent (Machirori & Fatoki, 2014). For Instance, Bancassurance products are life insurance, and they have high standards for customer satisfaction, perceived value, and customer relationship management, all of which lead to an improvement in the clientele's rapport with the bank (Iqbal et al., 2023). This is because, convenience is a crucial component of consumer satisfaction since it provides a suitable avenue for the buyer to fully comprehend the product (Iqbal & Jalees, 2016).

The strategic management process focuses on how businesses raise their level of awareness, establish their aims and objectives, put those goals into action, and assess whether they were successful. The approach provides the organization's members with a point of reference for the organization's expansion and development. A strategy is successful when it gives the organization a competitive edge, is viable, and generates value for all parties involved, including the players and stakeholders. Thompson (1995) noted that corporate or organizational culture and values,

as well as the strength and leadership style of the strategy's leader, all affect how well a strategy is implemented. Success would have been simpler if the organization's culture and values had adopted the change (Galabova, 2021).

According to the strategic brainstorming perspective, new strategic ideas are created as a result of the mental model of strategy and business operations (Hamel et al., 1999). Understanding how to position the company to take advantage of possibilities while reducing environmental risk is crucial. Executing the Synthesis of the alternative tactics, their potential effects, and results is necessary for the chosen strategies. (Anyakoha, 2019). The frequent and erratic developments on the world markets have rendered the linear approach to strategic management obsolete. Building and maintaining organizational resilience helps the organization maintain its resources and fortifies its capabilities in times of upheaval and change.

For instance, to establish and preserve enduring relationships with clients in accordance with their mutual goals, businesses may employ digital marketing communication platforms that foster communication among marketing partners (Fareed et al., 2023). Technological developments have pushed consumers to embrace the digital age, impacting information management, processing methods, consumer behaviour, and other aspects. The transition to the digital era has caused a reorganization of organizations' business environment and economics (Iqbal, 2023).

Customer loyalty and satisfaction should be prioritized as major goals in a company's strategic management approach. Companies may improve customer satisfaction and foster loyalty by developing strategies that are in line with customer demands and expectations. This could entail boosting customer service, personalizing experiences, or improving product quality. Businesses need to maintain their adaptability and use techniques that enable their staff to adjust and improve ineffective practices (Genus, 1995; Chandler, 1992).

The goal of strategic management should be to build enduring relationships with customers. Companies may encourage loyalty and improve client relationships by proactively addressing concerns and regularly assessing customer satisfaction levels. This could include rewards programmes, individualized deals, or top-notch customer service. Businesses can maintain a competitive edge by focusing on the customer

experience (Iqbal, 2023).

3. METHODOLOGY

This research performs through literature review as well as analysing the existing theories about loyalty among customers, their satisfaction, on strategic market management. The goal of this study is to draft a review work, which would involve going through existing literature as a method for research. Selecting relevant scholarly articles, books, and theories, critically evaluating them in order to review present knowledge and indicate areas for further research implies that the research design will also be involved in this study. Inclusion criteria would be peer-reviewed articles, books, and papers published over the last twenty years, and the exclusion criteria would be non-peer-reviewed sources, articles not in English, or studies that do not fall within customer loyalty and satisfaction (CL&CS) ambit.

This research examined theoretical, methodological, and topical soundness of chosen literature by evaluating key-words critically. To conduct analysis, look at methods used for conducting studies; discover findings derived from them as well as possible conclusions reached by authors at their conclusions part. The primary goal of this research is to enhance knowledge on ways in which strategic market management is influenced by customer loyalty and satisfaction, and to provide solutions that contribute to managerial practices or directions. This is to be achieved by evaluating the available literature and theories on the topic which are critical in determining the above influences for comprehensive comprehension thereby producing knowledge for scholars and business people.

4. CONCLUSION

Customer loyalty and satisfaction play a crucial role in shaping strategic marketing outcomes. Establishing a loyal customer base that is satisfied with a company's offerings is essential for long-term success. By cultivating customer loyalty, businesses can enhance revenue and profitability as satisfied customers are more likely to continue purchasing products or services. Additionally, loyal customers can become brand advocates, positively influencing others and attracting new customers. Moreover, satisfied customers provide valuable feedback and engage in repeat purchases, bolstering the company's market position. As a result, prioritizing customer satisfaction and loyalty within marketing strategies is vital for fostering

strong customer relationships and driving sustainable growth.

This may involve areas such that retail stores, banks, phones, and hotels; while its research will be broad, specific concentration will be given to particular industries and sectors in which customers' contentment and attachment are important. Derived from the collation of various readings and theories, this paper will in due course furnish companies with well-thought-out bits of advice on how they can boost their marketing management systems by coming up with projects that are meant to make sure that customers are pleased and at the same time administer loyalty programs.

A global perspective was taken in the research to consider how customers' satisfaction, and loyalty are influenced by different cultural, economic and social factors across various regions. This will increase the generalizability and applicability of findings.

Competing Interests

The authors did not declare any competing interest.

References

Anderson, J. C., & Narus, J. A. (1998). Business marketing: understand what customers value. *Harvard Business Review*, 76, 53-67.

Anyakoha, M. W. (2019). *Strategic management: The dynamics of excellence*. Routledge.

Aramburu, I. A., & Pescador, I. G. (2019). The effects of corporate social responsibility on customer loyalty: The mediating effect of reputation in cooperative banks versus commercial banks in the Basque country. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 154(3), 701-719. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-017-3438-1>

Bowen, J. T., & Chen, S. L. (2001). The relationship between customer loyalty and customer satisfaction. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 13(5), 213-217. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09596110110395893>

Chandler, A. D. (1992). Organizational capabilities and the economic history of the industrial enterprise. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 6(3), 79-100.

Fareed, S. A. Q., Jabbar, T., Makhdoom, S. F., & Iqbal, M. N. (2023). Influence of digital marketing on purchase decision: A qualitative study on Pakistani customers. *International Journal of Trends and Innovations in Business & Social Sciences*, 1(4), 122-128.

Fornell, C., Rust, R. T., & Dekimpe, M. G. (2010). The effect

of customer satisfaction on consumer spending growth. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 47(1), 28-35.

<https://doi.org/10.1509/jmkr.47.1.28>

Galabova, M. (2021). Strategic management in organizations. In *Emerging Trends and Innovations in Strategic Management and Leadership* (pp. 25-43). IGI Global.

Genus, A. (1995). Organisational strategy, environmental strategy and performance: A study of organizations in the UK water industry. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 45(3), 269-288.

Gupta, A., & Sahu, G. P. (2015). Exploring relationship marketing dimensions and their effect on customer loyalty-a study of Indian mobile telecom market. *International Journal of Business Innovation and Research*, 9(4), 375-395.

<https://doi.org/10.1504/IJBIR.2015.070176>

Gustafsson, A., Kristensson, P., Witell, L., & Johnson, M. D. (2015). Conceptualizing customer satisfaction as a multistage process spanning pre-purchase, consumption, and post-consumption. *Journal of Service Management*, 26(2), 206-231.

Hamel, G., Doz, Y. L., & Prahalad, C. K. (1989). Collaborate with your competitors and win. *Harvard Business Review*, 67(1), 133-139.

Herhausen, D., Kleinlercher, K., Verhoef, P. C., Emrich, O., & Rudolph, T. (2019). Loyalty formation for different customer journey segments. *Journal of Retailing*, 95(3), 9-29.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretai.2019.05.001>

Iqbal, M. N. (2023). A qualitative study on Bancassurance products and its implementation for efficient customer experience in Pakistan. *International Journal of Trends and Innovations in Business & Social Sciences*, 1(1), 24-29.

Iqbal, M. N., Shaikh, N. N., & Dilshad, W. B. (2023). An impulsive buying behavior of customer: a qualitative study on bancassurance services in Pakistan. *Priority-The International Business Review*, 2(1), 138-151.

Iqbal, N. M., & Jalees, T. (2016). Bancassurance: A potential project in the life insurance sector of Pakistan to achieve consumer trust and awareness. *Market Forces*, 11(1).

Izogo, E. E. (2017). Customer loyalty in telecom service sector: The role of service quality and customer commitment. *The TQM Journal*, 29(1), 19-36.

<https://doi.org/10.1108/TQM-10-2014-0089>

Joyce, P., & Woods, A. (1996). *Essential strategic management: From modernism to pragmatism*. Butterworth-Heinemann.

Khan, R. U., Salamzadeh, Y., Iqbal, Q., & Yang, S. (2022). The impact of customer relationship management and company reputation on customer loyalty: The mediating role of customer satisfaction. *Journal of Relationship Marketing*, 21(1), 1-26.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/15332667.2020.1840904>

Kohli, A. K., & Jaworski, B. J. (1990). Market orientation: The construct, research propositions, and managerial implications. *Journal of Marketing*, 54(2), 1-18.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/002224299005400201>

Körner, J., Wirtz, J., & Göttel, V. (2015). Understanding customers' satisfaction and repurchase intentions: An integration of expectations disconfirmation and attribution theory. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 43(5), 597-616.

Kotler, P. (2007). *Marketing management*. Pearson Prentice Hall.

Machirori, M., & Fatoki, O. (2014). Customer satisfaction: A dynamic framework. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(13), 275-282.

Magretta, J. (2012). *Michael Porter jasně a srozumitelně: o konkurenci a strategii*. Management Press.

Mura, L., & Slezia, J. (2015). Innovation and entrepreneurship network. *CERS, 2014*, 5th.

Nurfarida, I. N., Sarwoko, E., & Arief, M. (2021). The impact of social media adoption on customer orientation and SME performance: An empirical study in Indonesia. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 8(6), 357-365.

<https://doi.org/10.13106/jafeb.2021.vol8.no6.0357>

Oliver, R. L. (1997). *Satisfaction: a behavioral perspective on the consumer*. New York, NY: McGraw-Hill.

Terblanche, N. S., & Boshoff, C. (2006). The relationship between a satisfactory in-store shopping experience and retailer loyalty. *South African Journal of Business Management*, 37(2), 33-43.

<https://hdl.handle.net/10520/EJC22310>

Thompson, J. L. (1995). Strategic management: awareness and change. *Journal of the Operational Research Society*, 46(11), 1398-1398.

Wolter, J. S., Bock, D., Smith, J. S., & Cronin, J. J. Jr. (2017). Creating ultimate customer loyalty through loyalty conviction and customer-company identification. *Journal of Retailing*, 93(4), 458-476.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretai.2017.08.004>

Yi, Y., & Jeon, H. (2003). Effects of loyalty programs on value perception, program loyalty, and brand loyalty. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 31(3), 229-240.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0092070303031003002>

Zsigmond, T., Machová, R., & Zsigmondová, A. (2021). Strategic management from the perspective of SMEs operating in service sector. *Quality Innovation Prosperity*, 25(2), 37-53.

<https://doi.org/10.12776/qip.v25i2.1549>